

Difficulties of Teaching Speaking Competence in EFL Classes and Effective Methods to Overcome Them

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Abstract: The address of the head of our state emphasized the need to achieve a level that would allow students of any secondary school to learn English at a high level. In general, special attention is paid to the study of a foreign language in educational institutions. In addition, for this it is necessary to get acquainted with the practice of foreign scientists on the methodology of language teaching. The article discusses the main difficulties that secondary school students encounter in the process of learning to speak in English lessons, possible ways to solve them, including problem situations as the most effective method that corresponds to the age-related psychological and pedagogical characteristics of secondary school students. level students.

Key points: foreign language, speech, problem situations, learning process.

Introduction

Due to the rapid changes in the economic, political and social spheres of modern society, the standard stipulates that the study of a foreign language at school should ensure not only “the development of a value-based attitude to a foreign language as a means of cognition and the achievement of mutual understanding between peoples and nations.” [16], but also “the formation of communicative foreign language competence necessary for successful socialization and self-realization” [16]. Studying a foreign language involves the mastery of four types of speech activity, which include speaking, listening, reading and writing. It should be noted that speech is the most popular and difficult, since with its help communication is established, information is exchanged and mutual understanding is achieved between the participants in the dialogue. Therefore, teaching speech as an independent type of speech activity is one of the main goals of teaching foreign languages. However, in 2016, among students in grades 5 and 8 The results of the National Survey on the Quality of Education (NIQE) in English show a rather low level of development of oral skills (the percentage of tasks completed in the speech area is 24.2% and 19.2%, respectively), which indicates the presence of certain difficulties that adolescents encounter in the process of learning to speak in English lessons [17]. Domestic and foreign scientists who have dealt with this issue (IAZimnyaya, ENSolovova, P.Ur, T.Hedge) were able to identify a number of main difficulties that accompany the process of mastering oral speech in high school students. EN Solovova identifies the following problems that students face when speaking in a foreign language: Although students feel confident, there are often situations when they do not want to speak or express their attitude to the problem posed. Unequal opportunities for students in the process of communication. Active students who know the language well often speak, while other students speak very little or do not participate in the conversation at all. Use of the native language. Students often switch to using their native language because a foreign language sounds unnatural when communicating with classmates [13, p. 121]. The listed difficulties that middle school students encounter in the classroom are the reason for the low level of development of communicative competence. Therefore, oral speech is one of the skills that students have difficulty mastering in the artificially created conditions of the

Russian school. Penny Ur identifies the following methods to solve the above problems: Use group work. Use simple language during discussions.

Methodology

Careful selection of discussion topics and competent formulation of tasks. Use of instructions that establish the rules for participating in the conversation. Clear presentation by the teacher of the type of monologue / dialogue that should be obtained in the speech; compliance with the conditions for creating a given speech situation; the pre-constructed speech setting should be clear and concise; preparation of additional supports; planning the survey and dividing students into roles, pairs, groups according to their language capabilities; use of mutual assistance and mutual learning.

When writing the research paper, we used Songbatumis AM (2017), M. Abrar (2016), Pirmatova Sh.A. (2020), Toshboyeva FB, Abdulmatova ZA, Davron Turgunov (2018). At the same time, it is impossible to talk about the real competitiveness of a nation without fluent English, because English is currently the language of successful integration with the world stage. Today, the main requirement is for students to fully master the Kazakh language in the literary language, as well as to ensure excellent knowledge of Russian and English. According to Mumari Songbatumis, a young English scholar from Indonesia, a child can easily and fluently master the language at an early age. At the same time, the Ministry of Education and Science is paying attention to early English teaching, which is a correct requirement. Because the foundation of knowledge acquired by a student at a young age will be solid and strong. A teacher who has mastered language teaching methods will easily overcome obstacles, despite the difficulties. Currently, English teachers are using advanced world experience, new technologies and methods in language teaching to improve the quality of English teaching [1, 4].

The purpose of the study is to identify difficulties in learning a foreign language. To study the behavior and abilities of each student, their age and psychological climate. Find out what prevents your child from effectively learning a foreign language.

The main goal of the study is to develop a way to improve speaking skills and effectively master the English language. The purpose of the study includes solving the following problems:

1. Conduct a theoretical analysis of publications devoted to the problem of learning English.
2. Identify the barriers faced by English language teachers and consider effective ways to overcome the barriers.

Materials and research methods

In this study, we used the methods of description, observation and analysis. By reading the works of world researchers and comparing the methods used in teaching English in our country, we propose several ways to overcome the obstacles in teaching English through comparative research. A language teacher is one of the most in-demand professions. A teacher with the right education and experience has the opportunity to demonstrate your teaching skills, immerse yourself in an interesting culture, meet new people from different parts of the world and travel to countries you have never visited. As with any teaching job, teaching English as a second language is not without its challenges [3]. We fully agree with this opinion; English takes any student to a wonderful world and has many advantages for self-improvement and knowledge of the values of another country. There are many challenges in teaching English, which has become a global language. However, any teacher who finds the key to these problems will think about the best ways to learn a foreign language and will be able to overcome any obstacles by using effective, advanced technologies.

European scholar Liton (2016) noted in his study that both teachers and students face problems in learning English. The problems of teachers and students are poor English proficiency. Students face problems related to lack of motivation in learning English [4, 9].

Teaching English at the secondary school level is naturally very different from teaching at the higher and specialized levels of education, such as college or university. The differences can be found in many components of education, including the curriculum, the learning environment, the students, and the teaching or delivery of content. Since the teaching materials in elementary school are simpler, many people may think that this educational content is more accessible for children to learn. However, teaching English to elementary school students is difficult because elementary school students are young children who have not learned to take responsibility for their tasks as much as high school and college and university students.

Teaching a foreign language at school requires high professionalism, love for children, as well as effort and ability to provide material for students to successfully master it and show interest in the subject. This, of course, can be achieved with a certain effort, and practice shows that success depends not on experience, but on the teacher's enthusiasm, energy and interest [6, 8]. We would like to note that the obstacles that arise in the process of teaching English are the fact that students do not pay full attention to the lesson material, they quickly get tired during the lesson, they lose concentration in the lesson, and in most cases they do not show interest in the lesson being explained.

The problems found vary depending on the attitude of students, teachers, and the learning process. On the student side, research findings have shown that problems in learning English also occur among students. These problems include insufficient vocabulary mastery, poor concentration, lack of parental support, lack of discipline, and speech problems [1,7]. We would like to add to this idea that the increasing number of English teachers from year to year does not help to eliminate the obstacles to students' effective learning of English. Such obstacles can only be overcome through creative research and the use of new technologies.

Results and discussion

In teaching English, we, foreign language teachers, face a number of difficulties. Unreasonably developed textbooks, on the one hand, contain the same topics, but on the other hand, they are

overloaded with insufficiently explained grammar, are filled with unnecessary vocabulary for children, the tasks are too complicated. , and the texts are not written in a modern way, there are only minor difficulties in the language adapted for children [7, 10]. From this point of view, the language of school textbooks is indeed difficult. If the textbooks were understandable, simple and structured with issues that correspond to their interests, students would be interested in receiving quality education. This is because, in order to cover all the educational material in the curriculum, the teacher can lose students' interest in English by forcing students to complete complex, difficult language tasks.

Research results and discussion

“Human life has a limit, knowledge has no limit,” said the first President of the Republic of Kazakhstan, NA Nazarbayev. Our President emphasized that since English is the language of progress and technology, we must learn it. In addition, a new education system is being introduced in our country's secondary schools, the main purpose of which is to introduce knowledge into the world educational space. Today, new information technologies have been introduced in English. Its use as a means of increasing interest in the language is very effective. New technologies of teaching are currently being used in schools. As the content of education and the requirements for it change, it is almost impossible to improve the quality of education without such requirements. Therefore, it is necessary to introduce innovations, that is, to increase the activity of schoolchildren based on an innovative system, increase their self-confidence, develop their cognitive creative abilities, determine the qualities of their activity - confidence in diagnostic methods, and teach them to express their thoughts freely. themselves in the classroom and outside the classroom. This helps to identify norms, signs and indicators of innovative behavior. According to Balanskat, Blamire and Kefala (2006), most studies confirm that the use of ICT in education helps students to play an active role in the learning process instead of being traditional passive learners [6, 9].

Lack of motivation among students may be due to lack of support from parents. Mumari Songbatumis once told in detail about her experience when she caught a student who had not brought any books to school due to forgetfulness. On the contrary, other students deliberately left their books on the classroom table. According to Mumari Songbatumis, such things would not have happened if the parents of the students had monitored their children's education at home [1, 5]. Unfortunately, such problems also exist in our country. Here we would like to emphasize that the problems of teachers in teaching English to students are closely related to the responsibility of parents.

The biggest challenge is teaching the class with books. Most teachers do not understand the effective use of new textbooks. Teachers do not understand the basic principles of textbooks and use traditional methods [8, 9]. This is directly related to the general written and oral speech in the formation of reading skills in schoolchildren. Teaching a foreign language is based on a functional system. Therefore, it is necessary to take into account the conditions of use of the language being taught in the environment. To learn a foreign language, it is necessary to use the most innovative methods and traditional teaching aids.

The basis of a teacher's skill is vocabulary, or rather, the level of vocabulary and speech culture necessary to organize our thoughts. To do this, a teacher must first teach in a language that he knows well. The second condition is that students in grades 6-7 must be taught in an understandable language. Therefore, we must always take into account that teaching in an understandable language is a principle of professional development.

Interest in innovations is a basic internal desire. Students are interested in something new and unknown. Such activities mobilize the entire mind, internal strength and power of the student. Therefore, interest is an important factor in the formation of both educated and well-rounded people. "Does knowledge acquired through involuntary persuasion and coercion lead to a developed mind?" - say scientists. Therefore, learning should be in a state of primary voluntary interest. In this regard, English teachers are using advanced world experience and new technological methods in language teaching in order to improve the quality of English teaching.

The main idea of the article under consideration is to allow students to develop in a certain direction as a holistic system, the purpose of which is to teach these technological methods; person-centered education; from explanation to understanding; from monologue to dialogue; from social control to development; from management to self-management.

The main task of the teacher is communication, which opens the way for interaction between students, giving them creative freedom. Therefore, the use of new information technologies in the field of education in our country is the main goal. This is a system of technical means in the education system, new information and communication technologies and new teaching methods. Our President, in his "Address to the People of Kazakhstan", emphasized the need to solve the following problems in order to meet the educational needs of the information society in the 21st century: improving the quality of education through the effective use of computers, the Internet, telecommunications, electronics and multimedia electronic textbooks.

One of the main English language materials that schoolchildren learn is a list of words with meanings, known as a dictionary (Brown and Hatch, 1995). Vocabulary learning can be manifested in the study of simple topics such as the names of objects around us, fruits, animals, sports, playing games, and giving instructions. This can be difficult, since most students are learning English for the first time [1, p. 56]. Indeed, as Brown and Hatch say, in learning any foreign language, it is important to have an adequate vocabulary first. Improving the level of a student who is learning English for the first time and who is already fluent in a foreign language is not an easy task.

In terms of content, Scott and Ytreberg (1990), as cited in Arikan (2011), in their book "An Introduction to Teaching English to Elementary School Students", stated the following: 1) young learners' activities should involve body movements and content. emotions, 2) learners should experience the language they are learning by following rather than by following grammatical rules; 3) classroom interactions should promote interaction rather than competition, and 4) each

component should be planned, taught, and assessed differently in the classroom. These formulations were based on the differences in English learning between young people and adults [9]. If we focus on the problem discussed in the first paragraph, in most cases, language can be effectively taught to the stream of elementary school students through tasks involving body movements. This is because primary school students are often very energetic. Through games, music and multimedia, students' interest increases and they learn English with high enthusiasm. We would like to emphasize that it would be more effective and better to teach English to schoolchildren based on communicative experience. Organizing work to increase the interest of weak students in learning can be done by conducting group and pair work in the classroom. As for the fourth point of view, when planning a lesson, the teacher should change each lesson and plan it accordingly. The interests and needs of the student, rather than one-sidedly removing obstacles to learning English. He can also increase the student's motivation to learn English through various assessment methods [10,].

Conclusion

We conducted an online survey to find out teachers' opinions on the problems they face when teaching English as a foreign language. 40 English teachers participated in the survey. The use of new information technologies in the lesson increases students' interest in English and helps to overcome language barriers. Teachers were asked questions about teaching methods aimed at developing reading, spelling, speaking and listening skills. As is known, a major challenge facing language learners is speaking skills. Developing English is not easy. In the section on obstacles faced by teachers outside the classroom, we tried to identify the problems that teachers face. We considered some of the difficulties that students face in the extracurricular environment. These include: the lack of interactive whiteboards, subject textbooks, their incompatibility with age characteristics, etc. In the section on obstacles, we wanted to identify the difficulties that students face in the lesson. In the same section, using the same questions, we found out the teachers' opinions about the students: a) the main obstacle to the development of speech skills in Kazakh schoolchildren is shyness; b) using ICT in the lesson should help students learn to work independently, taking into account their physiological, intellectual and psychological characteristics; c) the practical application of new technologies opens up a new type of cognitive activity in students, as a result of which new knowledge is revealed.

The first part of the questionnaire revealed that the significant challenges teachers face in the classroom are related to building the foundations of students' ability to communicate in real-life English, the regularity of educational publications, and setting appropriate criteria for teaching objectives. The majority of respondents (60%) note the use of new information technologies in the classroom. We can increase students' interest in English and help overcome barriers to language learning. It is practical to use different types of work individually, in pairs, in groups, in the classroom, etc. Also, overcoming obstacles that arise in teaching a foreign language using effective methods depends on the teacher's skills.

The results of the second part of the questionnaire showed that: the majority of respondents (53%) noted that the problems that teachers face outside the classroom are the lack of interactive whiteboards, the inadequacy of subject textbooks for the age characteristics, the inadequacy of language classes. fully equipped for learning a foreign language. In this part of the diagram, teachers do not agree or disagree with the data obtained from the student survey

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